

Griffith University
Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

**WORKSHOP ON
DATING, ISOTOPES &
HUMAN EVOLUTION
(DIHE)**

25-27 September 2019

Ship Inn
Southbank, Brisbane

Acknowledgment of Country

Griffith University and the Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution acknowledge the people who are the traditional custodians of the land, pays respect to the Elders, past and present, and extend that respect to other Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples.

We acknowledge the wisdom inherent in Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Australians as the oldest surviving culture in the world, and recognise their custodianship of the land on which our campuses are located. Griffith strives to be a place where Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples are valued and respected, and where First Australian Peoples' cultures and knowledge form an integral part of our vision for learning, teaching, research and community engagement. We also recognise reconciliation is a shared process and that every student and staff member has a role to play in effecting positive change for a better, more inclusive Australia.

Griffith University promotes reconciliation, respect, education and engagement. It has the largest Indigenous-student population of any Queensland university.

The South Bank, Nathan and Mount Gravatt campuses are situated on the land of the Yugarabul, Yuggera, Jagera and Turrbal peoples. Logan is situated on the land of the Yuggera, Turrbal, Yugarabul, Jagera and Yugambeh peoples. The Gold Coast is situated on the land of the Yugambeh/Kombumerri peoples.

Contents

Acknowledgment of Country	1
DIHE Organising Committee	3
Student Assistance.....	3
Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution (ARCHE)	4
Our Sponsors.....	5
Workshop Venue	6
Public Transport in Brisbane	9
Closing Dinner	11
Statement on Ensuring a Safe and Inclusive Environment	12
In an emergency.....	13
Social Media guide	14
Programme	15
Abstracts	19 - 62

Introduction

In recent years, the application of micro-analytical techniques on human fossils have seen dramatic changes in our understanding of ancient humans and their environment. Direct dating has led to important revisions of the chronology of human evolution, for example, by establishing the oldest modern human at Irhoud (~ 300 ka), the earliest modern human out of Africa (Misliya at ~ 170 ka) and the ages of enigmatic fossils such as *Homo naledi* and *Homo floresiensis*. *In situ* isotope studies on Neanderthal teeth have also revealed insights into migration, seasonality, weaning and lead poisoning.

From 25 to 27 September 2019, the **Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution (ARCHE) at Griffith University**, Brisbane, hosts a three-day international Workshop on dating, isotope studies and human evolution (DIHE). The aim of this interdisciplinary workshop is to bring together internationally recognised specialists from a wide range of scientific fields to exchange results and ideas from their work relating, to a greater or lesser extent, to human evolution. The Workshop aims at encouraging scientific discussions around unsolved questions in the various disciplines and to explore new avenues for future research.

DIHE Organising Committee

- Chair: Dr Mathieu Duval - Griffith University (m.duval@griffith.edu.au)
- Prof. Rainer Grün - Griffith University (rainer.grun@griffith.edu.au)
- Ms Holly Smith - Griffith University (holly.smith11@griffithuni.edu.au)
- Mr David McGahan - Griffith University (d.mcgahan@griffith.edu.au)

Student Assistance

- Ms Brooke Emma Jensen – Griffith University

Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution (ARCHE)

ARCHE is a research centre within the Griffith University's [Environmental Futures Research Institute](#) (EFRI) and was officially launched in July 2016. EFRI combines science, innovation and local Australian experience to expand new knowledge through fundamental research.

ARCHE conducts some of the world's most comprehensive analyses of human evolution. We are the first academic centre in Australia specifically focused on gaining a deeper understanding of ancient human migrations and the full story of the origins of people in our region. Our mission is to foster research excellence through multidisciplinary projects that bring together leading international scholars and institutions in the field of human evolution, with a particular focus on two key regions: Australia and neighbouring Southeast Asia.

Our research covers archaeology, genomics, geophysics, geochronology, palaeoanthropology, palaeoecology and landscape evolution. ARCHE researchers are partners in high profile international networks. Our multidisciplinary projects span a number of sites across the globe. Collective findings are meshed together to provide comprehensive insights into human migrations and habitations throughout their prehistory.

Visit ARCHE here: <https://www.griffith.edu.au/human-evolution>

Our Sponsors

Formally founded in 1971, Griffith opened its doors in 1975, introducing Australia's first degrees in environmental science and Asian studies.

The university is named after Sir Samuel Walker Griffith, who was twice Premier of Queensland and the first Chief Justice of the High Court of Australia. Sir Samuel Griffith played a major role in the Federation of Australia and was the principal author of the Australian constitution.

Opening initially with the one campus at Nathan and 451 students, the University now has five physical campuses spanning three cities, the largest of which are the Gold Coast campus at Southport and the Nathan campus in Brisbane. In 2018, the University launched its Digital campus, now its sixth campus. Griffith has over 44,000 students and offers a full suite of undergraduate, postgraduate and research degrees in the areas of business and government, criminology and law, education, engineering and information technology, environment, planning and architecture, health, humanities and languages, music, science and aviation, and visual and creative arts.

Workshop Venue

Location: Griffith University South Bank campus

Address: The Ship Inn - Function Room (2nd Floor), Cnr Stanley & Sidon Streets, Brisbane

Griffith University South Bank campus ([map](#)) is within walking distance from Brisbane CBD (10-15 min). It is located next to the Maritime Museum, between Grey Street and the Brisbane River. Further information may be found [here](#). Except for the workshop dinner, organised at the West End Croquet Club, all the DIHE events will take place on the South Bank campus (see below).

Both the Ship Inn Function Room (2nd floor, building S06) and Lecture Theatre Room S05_2.04 have wheelchair access from the South Bank foreshore and Grey St. An elevator is located by the entrance to the Griffith Graduate Centre (S07) for access to the Ship Inn Function Room. Ramps connect disabled toilets to the lecture theatre directly past Security. There are also disabled toilets directly next to the lifts on all levels of building S07. **If any assistance is required throughout the workshop please speak to the workshop organisers.**

Event	Location
Ice breaker reception (17:00 24 th Sept)	Ship Inn Function Centre (2 nd Floor, Building S06)
Morning, Lunches and Afternoon teas	Ship Inn Function Centre (2 nd Floor, Building S06)
IMPACT Lecture (18:00 26 th Sept)	Lecture Theatre Room S05_2.04
IMPACT Lecture Reception	South Bank Campus Garden (courtyard next to the Lecture Theatre)
Workshop Dinner (18:00 27 th Sept)	West End Croquet Club

The Ship Inn, South Bank

Please go to our Level 2 Function Centre, entry via the Griffith Graduate Centre, directly behind the Ship Inn.
Enter through the glass sliding doors, up the stairs onto the first floor, turn right and back across the walkway.

Ship Inn Function Centre (2nd Floor)

Lecture Theatre Room S05_2.04

0 10m 50m 100m

- LEGEND
- INFORMATION /SECURITY OFFICE
 - TAXI
 - BUS STOP
 - PUBLIC PARKING
 - WALKWAY
 - FOOD & BEVERAGE
 - DELIVERIES ENTRY

Building Legend	
S01. Queensland Conservatorium	(D7)
S02. Webb Centre	(K3)
S03. Grey Street Studios	(K4)
S04. Rivers Studios	(J4)
S05. QCA Lecture Theatre & Gallery	(K4)
S06. Ship Inn	(K3)
S07. Griffith South Bank Graduate Centre	(K3)
S08. Griffith Film School	(L1)

Workshop Venue

8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1

Public Transport in Brisbane

Train or Bus

The South Bank area in Brisbane can be conveniently reached by Train or Bus. A TransLink journey planner is available at: <https://translink.com.au/>

Go card

The easiest and cheapest way to use Brisbane public transport is with a *Go* card. These can be purchased at convenience stores throughout Brisbane and can be used on trains, buses, and ferries. You can pay the driver with cash on ferries and buses. Train travel requires purchasing a ticket from a ticket machine or service desk at the train station prior to embarking.

From the Airport to Brisbane City

You can take a shuttle bus or taxi from the airport. The cheapest option is the Gold Coast train line from Brisbane Domestic and International airports to the CBD. It generally costs ~\$15 and takes approx. 20 mins (Network map may be found [here](#)). The workshop venue is located **near the South Bank train station**. A journey planner may be found [here](#).

A taxi will cost approx. \$50 from the airport to Southbank, and will take about 25 minutes. They can be caught immediately outside the terminal.

Travel Options from CBD to Venue

- ★ Conference Venue
- ★ North Quay Ferry Terminal (City Hopper and CityCat)
- ★ Southbank Ferry Terminal 2 (CityCat only)
- ★ Southbank Ferry Terminal 3 (City Hopper only)
- Route from CBD to venue
- Alternate route from CBD to venue

Brisbane River Ferries

A great way to get a feel for Brisbane is to catch a Brisbane River Ferries. You can either catch the CityCat or the City Hopper (**the City Hopper is free**). Timetable and the ferry routes can be accessed [here](#) and [here](#).

Depending on where you are staying you can catch a CityCat from Eagle Farm, past Newstead and around to the CBD and Southbank. If staying in the CBD you can catch the

CityCat or the City Hopper from North Quay. The CityCat will stop at Southbank 2 Ferry Terminal. While the City Hopper will stop at Southbank Terminal 3 (see image below). Both stops are within walking distance to the workshop venue. As you exit the Southbank 2 Ferry Terminal ramp, take a left and walk along the waterfront until you reach the Southbank Ferry Terminal 3. Here, take a right turn away from the waterfront, up through the hanging gardens until you see the Ship Inn Hotel. The Southbank Campus will be directly behind the Ship Inn Hotel (see the map below).

Walking options

If you are staying in the city there are two walking options. The first is to go across the Victoria Bridge and then south along the waterfront (red line on map). Or you can walk through the Botanical Gardens and take the pedestrian bridge over the Brisbane River. There is a cafe situated on the bridge where you can enjoy a coffee on the way (pink line on map).

Closing Dinner (BBQ)

The closing dinner (BBQ) has been organised in the **West End Croquet Club - 91 Cordelia St, South Brisbane**. To reach the Croquet Club by foot (red lines; 1.1km, 13-15 minutes) from the Ship Inn, walk away from the river along Sidon St until, at the top of the small hill, you turn right onto, Grey St. Follow Grey St for 700m before turning left onto, Glenelg St. After 400m, at the T-junction with Cordelia St, cross the road and 20m on your right you will find the West End Croquet Club, at the SE corner of Musgrave Park. From Glenelg St you can probably follow your nose.

Alternatively, the journey will take 3-4 minutes by taxi from Grey St. Or, bus number 198 from, 'Vulture St near Grey St, Stop 4' (red circle) to the 'Edmondstone St Hail and Ride' beside Musgrave Park, followed by a 350m around the southern margin of Musgrave Park.

Walking from Ship Inn to West End Croquet Club

Statement on Ensuring a Safe and Inclusive Environment

The Dating, Isotope and Human Evolution (DIHE) workshop is committed to providing an equitable, inclusive and accessible workshop free of discrimination, harassment, bullying, sexual harassment, sexual assault or vilification.

All workshop attendees are expected to behave respectfully and not engage in discrimination, harassment, bullying, sexual harassment, sexual assault or vilification.

Who to contact if you have a concern

The DIHE organising committee can be contacted at any time if there are any issues related to equity, inclusion, access and/or inappropriate behaviour at the workshop:

DIHE Organising Committee

Chair: Dr Mathieu Duval - Griffith University (m.duval@griffith.edu.au)

Prof. Rainer Grün - Griffith University (rainer.grun@griffith.edu.au)

Ms Holly Smith - Griffith University (holly.smith11@griffithuni.edu.au)

Mr David McGahan - Griffith University (d.mcgahan@griffith.edu.au)

Reporting issues related to Griffith visitors

Complaints against or from external visitors should be directed to the Vice President (Corporate Services) office via complaints@griffith.edu.au

Policy and procedures related to Griffith staff

Policies and procedures related to Griffith staff include, but are not limited to:

- [Code of Conduct](#)
- [Staff Sexual Assault and Sexual Harassment Policy](#)
- [Staff Harassment, Bullying and Discrimination Policy](#)
- [Reporting and Resolution of Staff Sexual Assault, Harassment, Bullying and Discrimination Procedures](#)

Policy and procedures related to Griffith students

Policies and procedures related to Griffith students include, but are not limited to:

- [Student Charter](#)
- [Student Sexual Assault, Harassment, Bullying & Discrimination Policy](#)
- [Procedures for Reporting and Responding to Student Sexual Assault, Harassment, Bullying and Discrimination](#)

Griffith University Security

Security services are available 24-hours on all Griffith University campuses and are handled by the [Campus Support Team](#). If the campus Security Office is unattended, a telephone is available at the front of each office to contact the team or alternatively **call 1800 800 707 (free call) anywhere on campus.**

A Griffith security office is located on South Bank Campus in S03 building, in the Courtyard next to the IMPACT Lecture Theatre S05_2.04.

For more information about Griffith Security, go to: <https://www.griffith.edu.au/security>

[Police](#) may be contacted where there is suspected criminal activity.

In an emergency

CALL: Fire, Ambulance, and Police on 000 or 112 from a mobile.

Social Media Guide

Wi-Fi

Complementary Wi-Fi internet is available at the Workshop venue for delegates. We will hand out Wi-Fi login details at registration. If at any time you cannot access the DIHE2019 Wi-Fi, please resort to [Eduroam](#) and Griffith University Public Wi-Fi.

Mobile phone/ recording devices

As a courtesy to presenters and those around you, please make sure your phone is on silent before entering the lecture theatre. Please do not take calls in the lecture theatre and do not use the flash to take photos during sessions.

For Presenters

If you have sensitive material in your presentation that you do not want recorded or you do not wish to be recorded or photographed, please make an announcement or use a slide to this effect at the beginning of your presentation. Please contact your Session Moderator if there is any violation of this.

For Delegates

Any recording or photographs should be for your personal use only and not for uploading to any social media or other online platforms, without the presenter's express permission, which you must request personally and prior to publishing.

The official Workshop hashtag is **#DIHE2019**

If you want to tweet about the Workshop, please include the hashtag **#DIHE2019** so that others interested in the Workshop can find your tweets.

Remember that many people present unpublished work at the workshop and you should use your best judgement when putting other people's research into the public sphere. You must also take seriously how you represent someone else's hard work and intellectual property online. Do not post photos of people, presentation slides, or posters without the prior and express permission of the individual/s or author/s. Respect the wishes of presenters if they do not want their paper to be tweeted and presenters please make it clear if this is your wish. Remember that Twitter is a public forum, so think twice when posting comments about the more social aspects of the workshop.

If you are on Twitter and are happy for people to tweet about your paper, you can put your Twitter username on your opening slide so the audience can accurately cite you online.

Programme

This programme may be subject to last minute changes. The definitive version will be made available at the workshop.

Tuesday 24th September			
Event	Time	Location	
Registration & IceBreaker	5.00-8.00pm	<i>The Ship Inn (function room upstairs)</i>	

Wednesday 25th September			
Event	Time	Name	Title
Registration	9.00am	<i>Location: The Ship Inn (function room upstairs)</i>	
Opening	9.30am		
	9.30am	John Graham (TBC)	Traditional Owner Welcome to Country
	9.45am	Andrew Smith, Rainer Grün & Mathieu Duval	Opening
Session 1		Chair: Rainer Grün	
1	10.00am	Malte Willmes	Tracing human and animal movements using laser-ablation strontium isotope analyses
2	10.20am	Katerina Douka	Using biomolecular approaches for the identification of new human fossils in the prehistoric record
3	10.40am	Qingfeng Shao	Applying a Bayesian approach for establishing the chronostratigraphy of the Yumidong Cave in the Three Gorges Region, southwest of China
Coffee break	11.00am		
Session 2		Chair: Robyn Pickering	
4	11.30am	Faye Liu	U-series dating of Dahongyan rock art paintings at Zhenfeng, Guizhou, southwest China
5	11.50am	Rachel Wood	Towards a pretreatment for radiocarbon dating tooth enamel
6	12.10am	Ian Williams	SHRIMPing Biominerals
7	12.30am	Tanya Smith	Fine-scale oxygen isotope measurements in primate teeth reveal ancient environmental variation
Lunch	12.50pm	<i>Location: The Ship Inn</i>	
Session 3		Chair: Renaud Joannes-Boyau	
8	2.00pm	Catherine Frieman	Bodies in motion: Telling social stories of mobility with isotopic data
9	2.20pm	Che Xiaochao	Multi-collector inductively-coupled plasma mass spectrometer U-series dating of speleothem in Panxian Dadong Paleolithic site, China
10	2.40pm	Rod Wells	A Diprotodon's Last Supper
11	3.00pm	P-J. Dodat (Speaker: Bruno Maureille)	First Ca isotopic composition of a Neandertal: Regourdou 1 (Montignac, France)

Event	Time	Name	Title
12	3.20pm	Jayne Wilkins	Human Evolution in the Kalahari: New Results from the North of Kuruman Palaeoarchaeology Project
Coffee break	3.40pm		
Session 4		Chair: Ian Williams	
13	4.10pm	Renaud Joannes-Boyau	Deciphering hominids palaeoecology using geochemical imaging of fossil teeth
14	4.30pm	Lee J. Arnold	Extended-range luminescence dating of hominin fossil deposits and lower to middle Palaeolithic sites from Atapuerca, Spain
15	4.50pm	Loïc Martin	Applications of LA-ICPMS imaging for U-series and ESR dating of Quaternary materials
16	5.10pm	Shin Toyoda	Heating, natural radiation, and provenance – the E1' center in quartz

Thursday 26th September			
Event	Time	Name	Title
Session 5		Chair: Katerina Douka	
17	9.30am	C. Lahaye (Speaker: Bruno Maureille)	Is Regourdou 1 fossil (Montignac, France) the earliest and most complete Neandertal specimen?
18	9.50am	Zenobia Jacobs	A high-resolution single grain optically stimulated luminescence chronology for Pinnacle Point site 5-6, South Africa
19	10.10am	Zhongping Lai	Chronology based geomorphological model provides solution for underground water arsenic pollution in Yangtze Plain
20	10.30am	Robyn Pickering	U-Pb dating speleothems from early hominin cave sites in South Africa
Coffee break	10.50am		
Session 6		Chair: Mathieu Duval	
21	11.20am	Julien Louys	Stable isotopic change in Southeast Asian mammals from the Middle Pleistocene to today
22	11.40am	Claire Ansberque	Rapid LA-Q-ICPMS characterisation of elemental distributions in apatite and the map interrogation tool "Monocle": implications for fission track analysis
23	12.00am	David McGahan	Behavioural adaptations in savannah chimpanzees and their relevance in human evolution
24	12.20pm	Andrea Ulrichsen	Mapping in the Pacific: The unique challenges of creating a strontium isotope map of Fiji and the Solomon Islands
Lunch	12.40pm	<i>Location: The Ship Inn</i>	
Session 7		Chair: Zhongping Lai	
25	2.00pm	Kelsie Long	High-resolution oxygen isotope records from fish and shell remains, Lake Kutubu, Papua New Guinea
26	2.20pm	Rainer Grün	Direct dating of human remains and the ever changing story of human evolution
27	2.40pm	Justine Kemp	Pleistocene human occupation on the "Empty Coast" of eastern Australia

Event	Time	Name	Title
28	3.00pm	Fang Fang	ESR thermochronometric evidence for accelerated Mid-Pleistocene exhumation of the Namche Barwa massif, eastern Himalayan syntaxis
29	3.20pm	H. Bocherens (Speaker: Bruno Maureille)	Neandertal stable Carbon and Nitrogen isotopes from the Quina Mousterian site of Les Pradelles (Charente, France)
Coffee break	3.40am		
Session 8		Chair: Bruno Maureille	
30	4.10pm	Jian-xin Zhao	Dating, isotope analysis and elemental mapping of archaeologically-relevant carbonates by LA-ICP-MS: Introduction to the RIF Lab at the University of Queensland
31	4.30pm	Verónica Guilarte Moreno	Electron Spin Resonance spectroscopy: technical advances and their application for ESR dating (X-band vs Q-band ESR)
32	4.50pm	Hannah James	Tale of two islands: bioavailable strontium mapping of Corsica and New Caledonia
IMPACT Lecture	5.30pm	Katerina Douka	When Neanderthals, Denisovans and modern humans met; What dating can tell us about human evolution <i>Location: Lecture Theatre S05_2.04</i>

Friday 27th September			
Event	Time	Name	Title
Session 9		Chair: Catherine Frieman	
33	9.30am	Rainer Grün	A very personal, 35 years long journey in ESR dating
34	10.00am	Bert Roberts	Human occupation and megafaunal extinction Down Under: some reminisces about Rainer's early years in Australia
35	10.15am	Mathieu Duval	35 years of struggle with ESR dating: a view from the younger generation
36	10.30am	Renaud Joannes-Boyau	Fragmentation of ESR dating: how two radicals threatened the fundamentals
Coffee break	10.45am		
37	11.15am	Steve Eggins	TBC
38	11.30am	Zenobia Jacobs & Robyn Pickering	Rainer's southern Safari: contributions to human origins research in southern Africa
39	11.45am	Malte Willmes	Building strontium isoscapes for archaeological provenance studies
Session 10		Chair: Julien Louys	
40	12.00am	Holly Smith	High-resolution computed tomographic imaging of cave breccia deposits from Southeast Asia
41	12.20am	Mathieu Duval	Huéscar-1 (Guadix-Baza basin, Spain), a palaeontological site illustrating the potential and limitations of the ESR dating method in Quaternary studies
42	12.40am	Steve Eggins	Cuddie Springs revisited (TBC)
Lunch	1.00pm	<i>Location: The Ship Inn</i>	

Event	Time	Name	Title
Panel discussion	2.30pm	The future of Archaeological sciences Moderator: Rob Bruce Panel members: Katerina Douka, Catherine Frieman, Zenobia Jacobs, Bruno Maureille, Tanya Smith, Jian-xin Zhao	
Workshop closure	4.00pm	Rainer Grün	
Coffee break	4.05pm		
Dinner	6.00pm	<i>Location: BBQ Croquet Club (Musgrave Park)</i>	

Abstracts

Rapid LA-Q-ICPMS Characterisation of Elemental Distributions in Apatite and the Map Interrogation Tool “Monocle”: Implications for Fission Track Analysis

Ansberque, C.^{1*}, Chew, D.¹, Drost, K.¹

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The ability of apatite to incorporate U at ppm concentrations makes it suitable for fission-track dating. However, the accuracy and precision of apatite fission-track (AFT) ages relies on the availability of un-zoned grains with high spontaneous fission-track densities. Unfortunately, natural samples often do not achieve this prerequisite, and using zoned and/or grains with low fission-track density is sometimes unavoidable, while exclusion of such grains is undesirable as it may bias the resultant fission track age. AFT dating by LA-ICPMS spot analysis works well for grains with homogenous U distributions, but is not ideal when apatites have too few spontaneous fission-tracks to detect U zoning, and on which it is difficult to decide where to place a representative ablation spot.

Here, we propose an alternative approach to the spot analysis that consists in producing a $^{238}\text{U}/^{43}\text{Ca}$ map of the entire apatite surface using the LA-ICPMS technique to capture intra-grain U-variation. Apatites are ablated with shallow (2 μm -deep) parallel raster lines using a two-volume cell laser connected with an aerosol rapid introduction system (ARIS). Elements were monitored with a quadrupole ICPMS, and include Ca, U-Th-Pb isotopes and trace elements (Mn, Sr, La, Ce, Sm, Eu, Gd, Lu). All data were reduced using the Lolite software, which creates 2-D maps (18 μm x 3.5 μm pixel-size) that are interrogated with the Monocle tool on a user-defined area. Standards include NIST612 silicate glass, and a series of matrix-matched apatite reference materials. AFT and U-Pb ages, and trace element abundances derived from the mapping approach are in good agreement with the literature at 2σ level. This mapping approach thus represents a new benchmark for future AFT analysis overcoming the “poor-quality-grain” issue. This approach may also be used to rapidly assess trace-element distributions in bio-apatite (i.e., teeth), and in screening carbonates prior to U-series analysis.

Extended-Range Luminescence Dating of Hominin Fossil Deposits and Lower to Middle Palaeolithic Sites from Atapuerca, Spain

Arnold, L.J.,^{1*} Demuro, M.,¹ Parés, J.-M.,² Duval, M.,^{2,3} Aranburu, A.,⁴ Ollé, A.,^{5,6} Sala, N.,^{2,7} Gómez-Olivencia, A.,^{7,8,9} Bermúdez de Castro, J.-M.,² Carbonell, E.,^{5,6} Arsuaga, J.-L.,^{7,10}

1. School of Physical Sciences, Environment Institute, Institute for Photonics and Advanced Sensing (IPAS), University of Adelaide, Australia
2. Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre Evolución Humana, Burgos, Spain.
3. Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution (ARCHE), Environmental futures Research Institute, Griffith University, Brisbane, Australia.
4. Departamento de Mineralogía y Petrología, Facultad de Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad del País Vasco/EHU, Bizkaia, Spain.
5. Institut Català de Paleocologia Humana i Evolució Social (IPHES), Tarragona, Spain
6. Area de Prehistòria, Universitat Rovira i Virgili (URV), Tarragona, Spain
7. Centro Mixto Universidad Complutense-Instituto de Salud Carlos III de Evolución y Comportamiento Humanos, Madrid, Spain
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The UNESCO World Heritage Atapuerca karst complex in northern Spain has yielded some of the earliest human fossils in Western Europe, the largest accumulation of Middle Pleistocene hominin remains globally, the oldest human mitochondrial and nuclear DNA recovered thus far, and >50 sediment-filled cavities preserving extensive archaeological sequences and faunal remains. Establishing detailed numerical chronologies on the Atapuerca infill sequences is essential for examining temporal relationships with other contemporaneous hominin records across Europe, and examining the climatic context of hominin evolution and major cultural turnovers over multiple glacial-interglacial cycles. Most of the fossil- and artefact-bearing sedimentary deposits in the Atapuerca karst system accumulated during the early to middle Pleistocene, and therefore lie beyond the upper age limit of conventional quartz optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating. However, the emergence of 'extended-range' luminescence dating techniques such as thermally transferred optically stimulated luminescence (TT-OSL) and post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence (pIR-IRSL) has opened up new possibilities for establishing numerical ages on the Atapuerca sedimentary deposits. Here we present an overview of our ongoing luminescence dating program at several of the Atapuerca palaeoanthropological sites, including Sima de los Huesos, Gran Dolina, Galería, Sima del Elefante and Galería de las Estatuas. We detail the steps taken to examine the reliability of extended-range

luminescence dating techniques at these localities, including independent dating comparisons, refinement of procedures to circumvent potential methodological complications (e.g. development of single-grain TT-OSL techniques), and application of multiple luminescence dating approaches in tandem to enable cross-validation of results. We also provide a synthesis of the most significant TT-OSL and pIR-IRSL chronologies obtained so far, including bracketing ages of 455 ± 17 ka to 426 ± 14 ka for the early Neandertal fossils at Sima de los Huesos and a single-grain TT-OSL age of 851 ± 46 ka for the *Homo antecessor* horizon (TD6-3) at Gran Dolina, in agreement with independent age control.

Neandertal Stable Carbon and Nitrogen Isotopes from the Quina Mousterian Site of Les Pradelles (Charente, France)

Bocherens, H.^{1,2}, Maureille, B.³, Royer, A.⁴, Costamagno, S.⁵, Beauval, C.⁶, Rendu, W.³, Garralda, M.D.⁷, Vandermeersch, B.³, Mann, A.E.⁸

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5. CNRS, UMR5608 TRACES, Université Jean Jaurès Toulouse II, Maison de la Recherche, 5 allée Antonio Machado, 31058 Toulouse cedex - France, costamag@univ-tlse2.fr
6. SARL Archéosphère, 2 rue des Noyers, 11500 Quirbajou - France, c.beauval@archeosphere.com
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Les Pradelles is a collapsed karstic cave excavated from 1967-1980 and 2001-2012. Quina type Mousterian lithics, reindeer bone fragments, plus many Neandertal remains (n=89) were uncovered. Artefacts and archaeozoology suggest the site was one of the very few excavated localations which was used as a hunting camp for processing predominantly reindeer carcasses. Many of the human bones show evidence of butchery activities. The site has been biostratigraphically correlated to MIS4 with absolute ages (OSL, TL) of circa 60 ka.

Research on stable isotope fractions of bone collagen from faunal and Neandertal fossils has provided data adding to our understanding of Neandertal behavior and diet (Bocherens et al., 1991). Recent results from a larger sample of humans (n=12), hyaenas (n=7), wolves (n=2) and mammoth (n=1) provide additional data to add to previously published results (Fizet et al. 1995). The new $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values are close to those previously published. A cluster analysis of the Neandertals and predators (hyaenas, wolves, foxes) divides them into 4 clusters. One cluster includes only Neandertals and corresponds to large bovids as preferred prey. Three Neandertal specimens cluster with some hyenas and one wolf and correspond to horses and large bovids as preferred prey. Another cluster corresponding to reindeer and large bovids as preferred prey contains only wolves and hyenas. The last cluster includes foxes and one wolf and may correspond to a preference for consuming small prey.

These new isotopic results suggest that the analyzed Neandertals had a strong preference towards large bovids as their main source of dietary proteins, with horse coming second. Reindeer seems to have been a minor source of proteins for the analyzed individuals. These results emphasize the use of multiple approaches for the reconstruction of Neandertal subsistence patterns.

Multi-Collector Inductively-Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer U-Series Dating of Speleothem in Panxian Dadong Paleolithic Site, China

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Panxian Dadong is located in the Liupanshui area in the western part of Guizhou Province, which is one of the most important Paleolithic sites in southern China. It used to be a very active vertical sinkhole with an underground river, a productive water system and a large number of cave deposits. In 1990, Panxian Dadong was first discovered to have human activities. From 1992 to 2000, Dadong carried out six excavations in cooperation with Chinese and foreign scientists. Four hominin teeth fossils were recovered, and the tooth damage level and tooth morphology were studied. In comparison with the world's mid-late Pleistocene humans, *Homo erectus* and modern humans, it is found that four hominin teeth fossils in Panxian Dadong are between the *Homo erectus* and the early *Homo sapiens* in morphological characteristics, and have shown early the variability of modern humans represents the type of transition of early *Homo sapiens* to modern Humans. The identical, within uncertainties, speleothem age of 130-300 ka have been reported by several studies. In this study, U-Th dating was carried out using a MC-ICP-MS in Radiogenic Isotope Facility at the University of Queensland, the corrected age of the fourth flowstone layer was 343 ± 106 ka, $^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}=3.87$, and the age of the stalagmites at the bottom of the digging hole inside of the Dadong was 406 ± 78 ka, $^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}=5.43$; 368 ± 135 ka, $^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}=3.37$. A small flowstone outside the entrance of Dadong obtain 440 ± 34 ka, $^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}=3.20$. Those above samples are almost in the same horizontal layer. Therefore, we suggest that the age of the Panxian Dadong Paleolithic site is more than 400 ka.

First Ca Isotopic Composition of a Neandertal: Regourdou 1 (Montignac, France)

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Since the first discoveries in palaeoanthropology, the nature of the relationships between human evolution and dietary habits has been a fundamental question. They are the subject of constant and diverse research from archaeozoology to isotopic geochemistry.

The development of accurate analysis of stable isotope ratios in geochemistry, particularly due to MC-ICP-MS, has now allowed the measurement of calcium isotopes on fossils. The Ca isotopic composition of mammals are defined by the Ca intake of the diet. In addition, Ca isotope analyses show a decrease in the $\delta^{44}/^{42}\text{Ca}$ between the feeding and the bone, which resulted in a reduction of the $\delta^{44}/^{42}\text{Ca}$ along the trophic chain. Recent studies suggest a difference between prey and predator close to -0.30‰.

As Ca is the essential component of the mineral fraction of bone, hydroxyapatite, the isotopic measurement of calcium requires a small amount of material (less than 100µg). For this reason, bone sampling for such a research can be considered as almost non-destructive.

Moreover, Ca has a very good conservation over time, which allow us to pass the limits of 100 000 years of the nitrogen isotope.

Following us, the Ca isotopic composition of a Neandertal specimen has not been studied yet. In this work, we analysed the Ca isotopic composition of the remains of one adult Neandertal, Regourdou 1 (Montignac, France), and associated fauna. To discuss the impact of the different calcium reservoirs we have also compared Ca isotopic composition of muscle, fat bone marrow, cortical bone and spongy bone on commonly eaten farming and wild species.

Our results suggest that Regourdou 1 diet was mainly meat based with a significant part of red deer as it has been recently proposed for Neandertals from this MIS 5 site.

Using Biomolecular Approaches for the Identification of New Human Fossils in the Prehistoric Record

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Over the last decade, the publication of genome sequences from Denisovans and Neanderthals, as well as the discovery of fossils belonging to previously unaccounted for human groups, have transformed our understanding of human evolution. Yet, large areas of the Late Pleistocene world, especially Asia, lack well-provenanced, reliably-dated and genetically-analyzed human remains.

In this talk, we will introduce an interdisciplinary project (“FINDER”) that applies a combination of analytical techniques to discover, characterize and analyse new hominin remains from several sites in Eurasia. At the heart of this work lies an analytical technique called collagen peptide mass fingerprinting, or ZooMS. ZooMS is a fast method that uses the internal variation of bone collagen peptides for the taxonomic classification of a bone. The method has immense potential in identifying hominin bone remains from highly fragmentary bone assemblages. Here we present examples from the application of this method to bones from several sites in North and SE Asia aiming to find new Denisovans and expand their geographic distribution in space and time.

35 Years of Struggle with ESR Dating: a View from the Younger Generation

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In November 2015, Rainer Grün gave an inspiring talk titled “35 years of struggle with ESR dating” at the 4th APLED Conference held in Adelaide. It perfectly illustrated the “beauty” of ESR dating, a quite complex method that may sometimes (when all planets align) provide reliable results. Still, there have been some significant improvements in our understanding of the ESR method since the early 1980s. In that regard, Rainer’s contribution has been essential, with a series of impacting, inspiring and influential methodological papers, which have acted as keystones in the scientific maturation of the younger generation of ESR dating specialists. I will present here a totally biased selection of the most significant contributions made by Rainer in the field of ESR dating. Of course, the opinions expressed in this talk will be the author's own and will not necessary reflect the view of the scientific community...

Huéscar-1 (Guadix-Baza Basin, Spain): a Palaeontological Site Illustrating the Potential and Limitations of the ESR Dating Method in Quaternary Studies

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Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) dating is usually not considered - with reason - as being one of the most accurate numerical dating method. Still, it can be applied to a wide range of Quaternary materials (carbonates, phosphates, silicates), which makes it very useful in many occasions. In that regard, the ESR dating study performed at the paleontological site of Huéscar-1 (Southern Spain) is an excellent illustration of how the method can contribute to address some key scientific questions of local or regional significance.

Located in the North-eastern part of the Guadix-Baza basin, Huéscar-1 has delivered a rich faunal assemblage made of >1200 fossil remains. A total of >30 taxa of large mammals, small mammals and birds have been identified, converting Huéscar-1 as a key palaeontological locality of major significance for both palaeoenvironmental and palaeoecological reconstructions in Southwestern Europe. In first instance, biochronological inference based on the study of the large and small mammal taxa suggested a late Early Pleistocene age estimate for the faunal assemblage. Moreover, the magnetostratigraphic study of a sedimentary sequence located nearby (Puerto Lobo) provided an additional indirect evidence supporting this chronology. However, a recent Luminescence dating study of the sediment enclosing the palaeontological levels yielded a significantly younger age of ~450 ka. These unexpected results shed a new light on the fossil assemblage and suggested potentially more complex bone accumulation histories than initially assumed at this site.

In order to obtain an additional and independent age control for Huéscar-1, and to understand better the origin of such a major discrepancy between the Luminescence chronology and the existing magneto- bio-stratigraphic framework, we performed an Electron Spin Resonance dating study of several quartz samples and a fossil tooth. The combination of the two ESR dating applications provides not only a direct age estimate for the fossils from Huescar-1, but also a burial age estimate for the quartz grains from the fossil-bearing deposits, which are directly comparable with the Luminescence results obtained from the same layers.

T.B.C.

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Cuddie Springs revisited (TBC)

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ESR Thermochronometric Evidence for Accelerated Mid-Pleistocene Exhumation of the Namche Barwa Massif, Eastern Himalayan Syntaxis

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The eastern Himalayan syntaxis at the collision boundary between the Indian and Asian plates is characterised by a clockwise structural deflection, active tectonism and intense surface processes. Rapid exhumation rates of ~ 10 mm/a within the past 1 Ma have been reported in the Namche Barwa massif, the northern third of the syntaxis, and in the adjacent Lhasa block to the north. The thermal history of the south side of the syntaxis is less well known. The first electron spin resonance (ESR) dating of quartz from a vertical transect near the southern boundary of the Namche Barwa massif has revealed an acceleration in cooling rate from 101 ± 12 °C/Ma at 526 ± 22 ka to 355 ± 35 °C/Ma at 166 ± 6 ka. Depending on the assumed geothermal gradient (50–100 °C/Ma), this is equivalent to an acceleration in exhumation rate from 1–2 mm/a to 3.7–7 mm/a. Thermochronometric data indicate that the late-stage domal pop-up of the Namche Barwa massif in response to the SW-NE shortening of the crust resulted in the coeval rapid cooling and exhumation extending to the north and south to the massif.

Bodies in Motion: Telling Social Stories of Mobility with Isotopic Data

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The last several decades have seen a revolution in methods for understanding human mobility. Between the increasing precision of isotopic data and the obvious power of ancient genetic information, we are seeing major narrative shifts in how we talk about the movement of people, ideas and technologies in the past. The scientific data emerging from these fields is rapidly diffused to the wider public through media and press releases, and is playing a key role shaping non-specialist understanding of the archaeological past. These stories of past people's movements catch the public interest because mobility in the present is highly politicised, regulated, and differentially accessible. Yet, our stories of mobility—driven as they are by scientific tools and laboratory analyses—often lack reflective interpretation. What does it mean for a person to have journeyed in the past or a migration to have occurred? How do we interpret patterns of mobility which appear to differ by biological sex? How might a past person or group's experience of mobility impact their identity? In this paper I will reflect on these questions through a series of case studies drawn from later European prehistory. My intent is to explore the social construction of mobility, its role in identity formation and the assumptions we bring from the present and apply to the results of scientific mobility studies of human remains. Scientific mobility studies have an incredible power to animate and humanise the long-dead whose remains we are privileged to study, I argue that a social element is necessary if we are to reconstruct the lives of people, rather than just identify bodies in motion.

Direct Dating of Human Remains and the Ever Changing Story of Human Evolution

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The development of nearly non-destructive dating has given access to many human fossils. The results have contributed to some major revisions of the chronology of modern human evolution. The dating of Irhoud pushed back the age of the earliest Homo sapiens to around 300,000 years ago. Direct dating also demonstrated that anatomical associations, for example for Homo floresiensis or Homo naledi, may lead to erroneous age assessments. This presentation will give an overview of the results published in the last three years, showing that the phylogenetic tree of humans has gained considerable complexity. It can be expected that new discoveries in geographical areas that have not yet seen systematic investigations will further contribute to the complex and exciting story of human evolution.

A very personal, 35 years long journey in ESR dating

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When I started in ESR dating, samples were irradiated with four additive dose steps of 5, 10, 15 and 20 krad and the linear extrapolation yielded the dose value. An assumed dose rate of 100 mrad/a yielded the age of the sample. Since then I learned that one actually has to measure the dose rate. I also learned that the dose response can be described by a single saturating function, or perhaps two, and that errors can be appropriately calculated. Rather than having a single anisotropic CO₂- radical, tooth enamel consists of two anisotropic CO₂- radicals and two isotropic CO₂- radicals, one stable, one unstable. Also, the dose response shows spatial differences in the production of these different radicals in response to beta and gamma rays. Then there is the problem of uranium uptake over time. We solved this by combining ESR and U-series analyses. We can even measure appropriate beta attenuation factors from sequential laser ablation U-series analyses. Even better, all analyses can be carried out on small enamel fragments, which can be glued back into their original position with little to no visible damage. Still, when using the most sophisticated dose rate calculations, they're often close to 1000 $\mu\text{Gy a}^{-1}$.

Electron Spin Resonance spectroscopy: technical advances and their application for ESR dating (X-band vs Q-band ESR)

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Since the development of Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) spectroscopy, X-band (9–10 GHz) has undoubtedly been the most widely used frequency in all different application fields. However, the constant progress of microwave technology has progressively opened a wide range of possibilities regarding the use of other higher frequency bands, such as Q-band, which can theoretically present a series of advantages compared to X-band.

In the last years, Q-band ESR (ca. 34 GHz) has being classically used for qualitative analysis, such as the characterization of chemical compounds/molecules. However, the potential of Q-band ESR for quantitative measurements has been scarcely evaluated so far. In particular, its application for dosimetry/dating purposes remains poorly known.

Hence, it is presented a comparative study performed on a series of fossil tooth enamel samples using both X- and Q-band frequencies. The performance of each technique (sensitivity, signal resolution, measurement precision and repeatability) has been thoroughly evaluated. The potential and limitations of X- and Q-band ESR for dose evaluation will be discussed.

A High-Resolution Single Grain Optically Stimulated Luminescence Chronology for Pinnacle Point Site 5-6, South Africa

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Few archaeological sites show detail of past occupation in as much detail as Pinnacle Point site 5-6. Occupation occurred against a backdrop of landscape-scale environmental and sedimentary processes that provide the broader context for finer-scale interpretations of the site formation history and archaeological patterns detected in the rockshelter deposits. This site documents three broad types of sedimentary deposit. The first chronicles occupations characterised by small groups and short visits in the form of single and intact hearths in a roof-spall dominated matrix. The second is represented by thick palimpsests of burnt remains, often disturbed by small gravity flows. The third correspond to predominantly aeolian sediments, sometimes deplete of any archaeological evidence. It has been proposed that these differences may be directly related to the relative level and proximity of the ocean to the site, and how intense occupation of the site might have been. Aeolian and palaeosol sequences are abundant in the vicinity of PP5-6 and these provide a partial view of the past landscapes available to the inhabitants of the cave. An important extension to the palaeo-landscape around PP5-6 currently lies submerged on the Agulhas Bank, as sea levels were lower than at present for the entire period of human occupation of PP5-6. In this presentation, we present a high-resolution single grain optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) chronology for PP5-6 constructed from ~200 sediment samples collected from individual stratigraphic units along the >14 m Long Section. We will describe the onshore and offshore geological successions around PP5-6 and correlate these with the sedimentary deposits inside PP5-6 and the high resolution speleothem record from nearby Crevice Cave. In doing so, we will place the archaeological record within a landscape-scale chrono-stratigraphic framework to examine how environmental and climatic changes may have regulated the presence or absence of humans in the rockshelter between ~100 and 50 ka.

Rainer's Southern Safari: Contributions to Human Origins Research in Southern Africa

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Rainer's first introduction to southern African archaeology and palaeoanthropology happened in 1988 when he and a number of other esteemed geochronologists, including Ann Wintle, John Vogel, Joel Kronfeld, Dorothy Godfrey-Smith, Siep Talma and Jerry Stipp went on the great southern Safari of archaeological and palaeoanthropological sites to meet, amongst others, Hilary Deacon, John Parkington, Peter Beaumont and Philip Tobias. As two products of the South African system (on either side of the boerewors curtain), many of these characters have played a major role in laying the foundations for our careers in both geochronology and prehistory, including Rainer. In this talk, we will provide a short tour of some of the major contributions he has made in southern Africa and reflect on their impact and influence on the next generation of South African researchers.

Tale of Two Islands: Bioavailable Strontium Mapping of Corsica and New Caledonia

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Mapping of bioavailable strontium in the environment allows for the investigation of archaeological mobility. This talk will cover the creation of bioavailable strontium maps for two islands, Corsica in the Mediterranean and New Caledonia in the Pacific, using plant and soil samples. Bioavailable strontium data from these two islands show different driving mechanisms, highlighting the importance of environmental mapping of strontium.

Deciphering Hominids Palaeoecology Using Geochemical Imaging of Fossil Teeth

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The mineralization of dental tissues is extremely valuable for reconstructing the early childhood ecological signal of extinct primate species. Each day the ameloblast and odontoblast cells, responsible for the formation of enamel and dentine respectively, deposit a new layer of tissue, thus creating a sequential record of the individual's life. The elemental intake and mineralization pattern of the dental tissues are strongly influenced by the individual's interaction with their immediate surroundings, often referred as exposome. Dental tissues therefore present a unique temporal record of the paleoecology of the individual early-childhood development. In this talk we will discuss the crucial role of fossil teeth to advance our understanding of human evolution in particular in reconstructing the ecology of our ancestors using isotopic and trace elemental mapping. We will present the recent advance made in investigating early-life record of our ancestors, discussing recent improvement in the methodology of elemental mapping, isotope analyses and software for the treatment of the signal. We will support our reasoning with concrete examples of key fossil analyses that led to new understanding of the palaeoecology and adaptation of extinct primate species.

Fragmentation of ESR Dating: How Two Radicals Threatened the Fundamentals

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In this talk we will look back on Rainer's push to reduce the destructiveness of ESR dating on valuable fossils, opening Pandora's box full of new challenges. Ultimately, the new direction led to an improved understanding of the ESR signal of tooth enamel including some important implications for age estimation.

Pleistocene Human Occupation on the “Empty Coast” of Eastern Australia

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Early modern humans entered Australia 60-70,000 years ago, and may have migrated along the coast to occupy the continental interior by 50,000 years ago. However, only four sites along the Australian east coast have occupation ages of >20,000 years, and each of these sites is limited by dating uncertainties. The absence of Pleistocene coastal sites has been interpreted as an absence of people on the grounds that coastal environments are unattractive and coastal resources uncertain during times of falling or lower sea levels – the “Empty Coast” hypothesis. The main problem may be incidental reporting from surficial, Holocene landforms rather than sites of known Pleistocene origin such as the Last Interglacial shoreline. This feature has differential preservation as fluvial, back barrier, marine and foredune sand complexes between Moreton Bay in Queensland and the Hunter River in central New South Wales. Here we present new results from one ancient site that provides archaeological evidence for at least 30,000 years of Aboriginal occupation in the coastal hinterland. The prospects for a targeted investigation of Pleistocene landforms elsewhere along the coast are explored.

Is Regourdou 1 Fossil (Montignac, France) the Earliest And Most Complete Neandertal Specimen?

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In 1957, a set of Neandertal bones, representing a young adult – Regourdou 1 – was discovered near the western wall of a collapsed karstic cave, the site of Regourdou, on the top of the Lascaux hill (Montignac, France).

The excavation of a large part of the site, under the supervision of E. Bonifay between 1961 and 1964, permitted the identification of an important lithostratigraphy (layers 8 to 1 from the bottom to the top of the sedimentological filling) and to propose the hypothesis of the association of the Neandertal remains to layer 4. Roe deer, wild boars, brown bears and a few Mousterian lithics were also found in this layer.

Since 2013, new investigations have been conducted at Regourdou and have allowed the identification of many new hominin remains from the 1961 to 1964 faunal collections. Regourdou 1 is now one of the most complete Neandertal skeletons from Western Eurasia.

If E. Bonifay (1968) considered that Regourdou layer 4 was related to Marine Isotopic Stage 5, this hypothesis was only based on the study of the succession of large mammal faunal associations from layers 4 and 2, as no absolute dates were available.

During our 2015 field campaign we obtained OSL and IRSL dates from layer 3, a very specific sedimentological facies just overlying layer 4, and preliminary OSL results for layer 4 observed in the northeastern part of the site. Layer 3 is considered to be around 80 ka and layer 4 around 91 ka, and thus related to isotopic stage 5c.

As a direct consequence of these results, Regourdou 1 is now the most complete and best-preserved associated individual skeleton of the entire Neandertal lineage.

U-series Dating of Dahongyan Rock Art Paintings at Zhenfeng, Guizhou, Southwest China

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Rock art Paintings are among the most important signs of prehistoric human (i.e. modern *Homo sapiens*) activities. Their studies have important implications for revealing human mind and behaviour evolution, reconstructing prehistoric human migration routes, and understanding the origins and evolution of ancient civilizations and art histories. However, due to the diversity of rock art paintings and the late modifications by the complicated environmental changes, rock art dating is still quite limited in China, and those recently dated sites appear to be significantly younger than counterparts in Indonesia (dated to ~40 ka). This seems to be contradictory to the widely accepted consensus on the arrival of modern *Homo sapiens* in South China at least 70-100 ka ago. In this study, we use both solution and laser-ablation MC-ICPMS *in situ* U-series dating techniques to date calcite travertines either overlying or underlying the rock-art painting pigment layers on the Dahongyan cliff within Zhenfeng county, Guizhou province, southwest China. Our preliminary age dating shows some hand stencils on Dahongyan cliff were at least older than 10 ka, representing one of the oldest so far dated for rock art paintings in China.

High-Resolution Oxygen Isotope Records from Fish and Shell Remains, Lake Kutubu, Papua New Guinea

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Lake Kutubu is an oligomictic freshwater lake, situated in limestone karst in the southern highlands province of Papua New Guinea. The region derives its high annual rainfall from the Northwest Monsoon and Southeast Trade Winds throughout the year and is sensitive to changes in the strength of Indian Ocean Dipole and El Niño-Southern Oscillation.

Here we focus on exploring the potential for deriving a long-term and continuous stable isotope record from fish and shell remains preserved in Holocene sediments cores from Lake Kutubu. The main aim of the project is to expand our understanding of past palaeoclimate drivers, landscape dynamics and lake system productivity, all of which would have influenced patterns of human occupation, dispersal and environmental interactions through time. The first part of the project explores the relationships between isotopic changes in modern fish and shell remains and known lake conditions. We measured oxygen isotopes across the age increments of modern fish otoliths and shells collected from Lake Kutubu, using the Sensitive High Resolution Ion Microprobe (SHRIMP). Freshwater snail shells from the lake sediment cores have also been analysed for oxygen isotope ratios, to determine if any past fluctuations in ambient conditions are preserved. Here I will present the results of these initial oxygen isotope measurements and discuss their relationship to ambient lake conditions, known climatic events and the possibilities of extending the record further back in time.

Stable Isotopic Change in Southeast Asian Mammals from the Middle Pleistocene to Today

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Carbon and oxygen isotopes provide important insights into past vegetation and climate. The analyses of these data from the Neogene of African mammals have provided compelling evidence of the major emergence of C4 grasslands and their impacts on mammal communities, and especially hominin evolution. Despite increased appreciation of the importance of Southeast Asia for understanding human evolution and migration, there remains comparatively little information on the environmental framework under which these occurred. The hypothesised savannah corridor running through the centre of Sundaland during glacial periods remains little tested, and any major vegetation shifts poorly understood. This is in part due to limited modern comparative data with which to compare the fossil record. Here, we present the results of carbon and oxygen isotopic analyses of the largest range of modern Southeast mammals assembled to date. We compare these results to published isotopic analyses of Middle and Late Pleistocene faunas from throughout the region and describe the ecological changes that have occurred over this time.

Applications of LA-ICPMS Imaging for U-Series and ESR Dating of Quaternary Materials

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Recent developments in both laser ablation technique and inductively coupled mass spectrometry enable now high-resolution and accurate spatial mapping of uranium and thorium isotopes in Quaternary material, even for concentrations below the ppt level.

By combining image processing and mapping, it becomes possible to accurately date minerals and biocarbonates without any chemical preparation, even with samples exhibiting very low uranium content and poor preservation. Image analysis enables the identification of leached or contaminated domains, as well as the correction for incorporation of detrital thorium. The amount of material required for such analysis is minimum (mg level or below), which makes this approach especially relevant for repeated micro-sampling on highly valuable materials.

Isotope mapping can also be of special interest for combined U-series and ESR dating of fossil tooth enamel, although never directly tested. The spatial heterogeneity of Uranium-series elements and the geometry of the tooth considered may be combined and modelled via Geant4 Monte Carlo, resulting in spatially-resolved incorporation parameters, as well as beta and alpha dose rates distribution in the enamel. The resulting US-ESR and CSUS-ESR age estimates may sometimes be significantly different to those derived from the standard approach based on bulk U-series analysis of each dental tissue.

Behavioural Adaptations in Savannah Chimpanzees and their Relevance to Human Evolution

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The chimpanzees from Fongoli, Senegal, uniquely inhabit a desolate, arid environment, similar to that experienced by Plio-Pleistocene hominins of equatorial Africa. It is generally agreed that a Plio-Pleistocene climatic shift from forest to savannah led to behavioural adaptations in African hominins. These hominins likely endured constant stress in an increasingly harsh environment. These stressors, and subsequent adaptive behaviour, probably drove phylogenetic events that shaped who we are today. However, the specific influence and effects of climate change and aridity on hominin adaptive evolutionary processes is not yet understood. Chimpanzees, are typically wet forest dwelling, however, in an arid, dry savannah, the Fongoli community exist at the physical and physiological limit of their species. Therefore, exposed to the similar stressors that drove Plio-Pleistocene hominin innovation, the Fongoli chimpanzees may provide a uniquely valuable model for understanding early hominins' behavioural adaptations to hot and desolate savannah environments. This research has built 3-dimensional models for humeri and femora of five adult *Pan troglodytes verus* (western chimpanzees) individuals from Fongoli, and neighbouring Dindefelo, Senegal (the only collection of its kind in the world). This project seeks to investigate intraspecific adaptive variability in the long bone cross-sectional geometry and shape in savannah chimpanzees when compared against forest-dwelling *P. t. verus*, then more broadly against forest *Pan troglodytes ssp.* (represented by Eastern and Central African chimpanzees). Finally, long-bone cross-sectional geometry and shape of savannah and jungle chimpanzees will be compared against African Plio-Pleistocene hominins. Through these analyses, this project endeavours to understand the influence of climatic change and aridity on behavioural patterns of Plio-Pleistocene hominin species.

U-Pb Dating Speleothems from Early Hominin Cave Sites in South Africa

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South Africa holds a rich record of human evolution, from our early hominin ancestors to the beginnings of modern human behavior in the MSA. The caves, known collectively as the 'Cradle of Humankind', located north of Johannesburg, preserve sediments and fossils of at least four species of early hominins and a rich diversity of other fauna. Despite playing an early, leading role in the field of palaeoanthropology, these sites and their fossils took a back seat to the discoveries coming out of east Africa. This is almost entirely because the South African caves, without the interbedded volcanic tuff layers of east Africa, were perceived to be undatable. The caves do, however, preserve speleothems, and the horizontally bedded, layered expression of these, known as flowstones, are found interbedded with the fossil bearing sediments. Speleothem chronology, using U-Th dating is well established, as is U-Pb dating of older, silicate material but the intersection of these two fields provided the first, direct and precise chronology for the South African caves and fossils. Dating 'young' 1-2 Ma, speleothems by U-Pb is challenging and limited by the distribution and concentration of U within the flowstones. Some kind of pre-screening, using passive phosor-imaging or laser ablation trace element mapping, greatly increases the chance of successful dating. Speleothems are known to only form under specific external conditions, the most dominant being an increase in effective precipitation; meaning that their presence alone in a cave sequence can be interpreted to represent a wet climatic phase. By extension, the sediments, always found interbedded with the flowstones in the South African caves, must represent accumulation during drier climate phases. This implies that the entire South African early hominin record from these sites carries an inherent dry bias and places the hominins in a community of arid adapted fauna and flora.

Human Occupation and Megafaunal Extinction Down Under: Some Reminiscences About Rainer's Early Years in Australia

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When Rainer joined the Australian National University in the early 1990s to lead its Radiocarbon Dating Laboratory, the known antiquity of human occupation of Australia had just been pushed back to between 60,000 and 50,000 years ago. This new chronology was based on thermoluminescence dating of sediments deposited in a rock shelter (Madjedbebe, but known then as Malakunanja II) located at the top end of the Northern Territory. The fact that people had been living in Australia at a time beyond the range of radiocarbon dating placed a premium on the use of alternative methods for age estimation of archaeological deposits, artefacts and fossils—including the remains of the giant marsupials, reptiles and birds that once roamed the continent and that some researchers thought had likely disappeared soon after human arrival. Rainer's arrival at ANU marked a watershed in Australia's development and application of these extended-range numerical dating methods, including his pioneering work in electron-spin resonance and uranium-series dating of human and megafauna fossils. Rainer's most influential dating projects in Australia include his ESR and U-series studies of human remains at Lake Mungo (1998–2000) and of megafauna fossils in southeastern Australia (2001–2010). In our talk, we will consider the legacy of Rainer's early research Down Under, set within the broader context of current best estimates for the antiquity of human occupation of Australia and the time of extinction of the continent's megafauna.

Applying a Bayesian Approach for Establishing the Chronostratigraphy of the Yumidong Cave in the Three Gorges Region, Southwest of China

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Yumidong Cave is a newly discovered Palaeolithic site in the Three Gorges region of the Yangtze River in the southwest of China. The excavations at this site during 2012 and 2013 led to the discovery of a large number of palaeolithic artifacts and faunal remains, attributed to the typical middle Pleistocene *Ailuropoda-Stegodon* fauna. The cave deposits are (>5 m thick) mainly composed of clay and limestone breccia, and divided into 18 archaeological layers from the top to the bottom. In the present study, C-14 dating was applied to 3 bones and 3 charcoal samples. U-series dating was used for 9 bone samples, 16 in-situ deposited secondary carbonates and 11 speleothem fragments that fallen from the cave roof. Coupled ESR/U-series dating was used to seven herbivorous fossil teeth. The C-14 and the coupled ESR/U-series age estimates were considered as the direct dating on the corresponding layers. The U-series age estimates obtained on the bones and the in-situ deposited secondary carbonates were used as the minimum age estimates. The U-series ages of the speleothem fragments were the maximum age estimates. Chronological modeling was performed with the ChronoModel, a newly available Bayesian age modeling software. The modeling is based on a hierarchical Bayesian statistical approach, which is aimed at estimating the date of a target event from the combination of individual dates derived from relevant dated events in such a way that it is robust to outliers. The Bayesian data analysis of the Yumidong cave provided the interval with a probability 95% for the layers: L2 (61–14 ka), L3-5 (82-150 ka), L10 (154-228 ka), L11 (186-265 ka), L12 (230-270 ka) and L13-15 (228-282 ka).

High-Resolution Computed Tomographic Imaging of Cave Breccia Deposits from Southeast Asia

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There is a considerable dearth of research focussing on spatial distribution of the cave breccia deposits of Southeast Asia. This taphonomic evidence can be critical to evaluate palaeoenvironments and the agents responsible for site formation events, especially considering that multiple taphonomic agencies may have modified the fossil assemblage. Tomographic imaging can be used as a macro-taphonomic approach to determine the degree of alteration and diagenesis of an assemblage, revealing the significance of potential agents responsible for site formation events. Such agents can include hominins, which is especially important as the complex depositional histories of the cave sites in Southeast Asia can obscure traces of hominin activity. Non-invasive thermal-neutron computed tomographic (CT) imaging allowed for three dimensional imaging of thirteen high-density Pleistocene breccia deposits excavated from Ngalau Lida Ajer, Ngalau Gupin and Ngalau Sampit caves in the Padang Highlands of western Sumatra, Indonesia. Tomographic reconstruction of the raw data was performed using VGStudio Max 3.3 software, rendering three dimensional images from the two-dimensional CT scans of the breccia deposits. The relationships between the clasts and other inclusions within the breccia deposits were analysed within their matrix before any destructive preparation. Preliminary analysis has revealed variable clasts from medium (1-2 cm) to large (>2 cm) that have undergone primary deposition, fragmentation, transport and re-deposition. These clasts include fossil bone and teeth that have been cemented in breccia of fluctuating density. The material show a preferred orientation that is indicative of strong uni-directional water action. The non-destructive digital imaging method used in this research has revealed evidence of complex vertebrate-bearing breccia formation in the caves of Southeast Asia at the macroscopic level that would otherwise have been destroyed using conventional excavation methods. This new evidence could strengthen our understanding of the ancient rainforest migrations and occupation by early humans and associated palaeofauna in Southeast Asia.

Fine-Scale Oxygen Isotope Measurements in Primate Teeth Reveal Ancient Environmental Variation

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Oxygen isotopes in tooth enamel vary with temperature, precipitation, and evaporation cycles during an organism's development, aiding reconstructions of past environments. Enamel is typically sampled by micro-drilling, yielding samples that integrate long formation times of unknown chronological age and limiting the recovery of seasonal environmental patterns from teeth. To address this dilemma we employ a Sensitive High Resolution Ion Microprobe (SHRIMP SI), measuring oxygen isotope compositions ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) from tooth enamel on a spatial scale of 15-20 μm , which can be related to daily increments and therefore formation times. $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of sheep enamel measured by SHRIMP SI are nearly identical to those from silver phosphate microprecipitation, confirming the fidelity of this approach for oxygen recovery. Here we analyze two fossil orangutan (*Pongo* sp.) teeth from Lida Ajer, Sumatra – the site that yielded the oldest insular Southeast Asian human remains 63-73 ka, as well as two molars of the 17 ma eastern African hominoid *Afropithecus turkanensis*. Molars were sectioned and sampled along the enamel-dentine junction on a spatial scale corresponding to a near-weekly timeframe using secondary-ion mass spectrometry. Standardized $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values were related to temporal records of formation over 3–4 years per tooth. Concurrently forming left and right molars from the same fossil orangutan ranged from 15.4 to 20.1 ‰ and 15.1 to 19.9 ‰ (VSMOW), falling within the range of modern Bornean and Sumatran orangutans, and supporting the fidelity of this palaeoclimate record. $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values in *A. turkanensis* exceed modern orangutans and chimpanzees, with approximately annual cycles that suggest drier and/or warmer climates than contemporary equatorial regions. Our data demonstrate substantial seasonal variability at a single locality. Future research on slow-growing primate teeth may help to establish whether seasonal environmental variation has been a significant force in great ape and human evolution from the Miocene to the present.

Heating, Natural Radiation, and Provenance – the E_1' Center in Quartz

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The E_1' center is one of the most fundamental paramagnetic lattice defects commonly observed in natural quartz, which is an unpaired electron trapped at an oxygen vacancy. The signal was once thought to be useful for dating of geological faulting, assuming that the signal is erased by the event to be dated and that the signal is enhanced by natural radiation as a usual dating signal does. However, it is well known that the signal is enhanced by heating, and recently Toyoda and Amimoto (submitted) showed that, though depending on the pretreatment, the signal intensity sometimes decreases with irradiation. It is necessary to consider the diamagnetic oxygen vacancies with two electrons, which are the precursors of the E_1' center, to understand the behavior of the E_1' center.

While the E_1' center should not be used for dating, it would be useful in Archaeology in the following three applications. The first is to estimate the heating temperature in the past by observing the signal intensity ratio of the E_1' center to the oxygen vacancy. If the archaeological heating was below 300°C, the signal will increase with laboratory heating, while it will not when the heating was above 300°C, where the ratio will indicate the heating temperature in both cases. If the heating was above 600°C, the E_1' center will not be regenerated after irradiation and heating because the oxygen vacancies were erased. The second would be to estimate the natural radiation environment. As pointed by Toyoda and Amimoto (submitted), the natural signal intensity of the E_1' center would be the result of the balance of the temperature and the dose rate of the environment where the sample has been placed. The last application would be to estimate the origin of the material which contains quartz, as done in sediment provenance studies.

Mapping in the Pacific: The unique challenges of creating a strontium isotope map of Fiji and the Solomon Islands

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Strontium isotope ratios ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) have gained recognition as a powerful tool of geolocation in bioarchaeological, ecological, and forensic studies. However, their application in bioarchaeological mobility studies is contingent on knowing the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope variations in the landscape. In recent years there have been an increase in the development of large-scale models of spatial isotopic variation predominantly in Europe and America. These maps have proven crucial for a more nuanced reconstruction of past mobility patterns and land-use. Strontium isotope analysis have been increasingly implemented in the study of inter-island mobility in the Pacific, however, several cite the lack of available strontium baseline data as a major limitation. In order to establish a baseline of bioavailable strontium around Fiji and the Solomon Islands, 330 plant and soil samples were collected from 165 localities across the islands. This paper will discuss the practical and methodological issues on how to approach the development of a strontium isotope 'isoscape'. When completed, the bioavailable Sr isoscape will represent the first nation-wide reference-set of Fiji and the Solomon Islands, offering the opportunity to further explore the inter-and-intra island mobility in the Pacific.

A Diprotodon's Last Supper

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Remnants of what were deduced by A.H.C. Zeitz in 1893 to be the gut contents of a *Diprotodon optatum* were located (stored in newspaper) in the South Australian Museum. Consisting of leaves, stalks and small twigs, they had been collected from the rib cage of a Diprotodon that had mired in the bluegreen clays at that "veritable necropolis of gigantic extinct marsupials and birds" Lake Callabonna, South Australia. These dry plant remains were subjected to experiments involving radiocarbon dating and stable isotope analysis. Samples of the gut contents were treated with a series of chemical pre-treatments using chlorite and hypochlorite reagents for AMS measurements on the ANU accelerators. These yielded dates exceeding 50,000 BP.

Modern plants for comparison were collected from locations near the lake, and were treated with hypochlorite to remove bark and most of the non-cellulose wood. It is clear from these results that the most likely food being consumed by the Diprotodon was *Atriplex* spp., saltbushes following the C4 photosynthetic pathway.

Human Evolution in the Kalahari: New Results from the North of Kuruman Palaeoarchaeology Project

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The southern African Middle Stone Age (MSA) archaeological record is transforming our understanding of *Homo sapiens* origins and evolution, but the intensity of research on coastal and near-coastal MSA records has outweighed that of the deep interior. As a multidisciplinary investigation of human evolution in the southern Kalahari Basin, South Africa, the North of Kuruman Palaeoarchaeology Project was initiated to help correct this bias. Here, we report results from our survey program and the excavation of new archaeological sites. At Ga-Mohana Hill North Rockshelter (GHN) we have recovered stratified MSA deposits. We show that the deposits are in good context with minimal disturbance based on stratigraphy, artifact density distribution, and fabric analyses. The lowest deposit provides early evidence for the use of symbolic resources and liquid storage containers. Our work at the open-air site of Witberg 1 has revealed an early Middle Stone Age deposit in primary or near-primary context. Optically stimulated luminescence analysis is providing high-resolution age estimates for the archaeological deposits. Uranium-series dating of extensive carbonate deposits is producing a record of past environments. This ongoing collaborative work is generating a diachronic record of MSA human-environment interaction in the Kalahari Basin that will allow us to assess the competing hypotheses about the origins and evolution of our species.

Shrimping Biominerals

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The SHRIMP ion microprobe has a justified reputation for its work on U-Pb geochronology, but its capabilities in measuring the isotopic composition of light elements (e.g. S, O, C) are less well known. Techniques initially developed for the microanalysis of stable isotopes in rocks are equally applicable to analysing biominerals. Conodonts, for example, are phosphatic marine microfossils, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of which is an ideal proxy for Palaeozoic sea surface temperatures. Conventional bulk analyses require milligrams of scarce fossils for a single measurement—SHRIMP needs only 5 conodont elements to measure $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ with a precision of $\sim 0.3\%$ (equivalent to $\sim 1.3^\circ\text{C}$), and multiple analyses on each element provide a test for inter- and intra-element isotopic homogeneity. Rainer Grün was quick to recognise the potential applications of SHRIMP to archaeology, encouraging exploratory work on otoliths and human teeth. This work was soon followed by a major project on otoliths from freshwater fish as a monitor of changing environmental conditions in Australian inland rivers and lakes, particularly Lake Mungo. A second major project involved the use of human teeth from a variety of burial sites to examine migration, cultural diversity and aspects of the Caribbean slave trade. These projects established SHRIMP as the SIMS of choice for biomineral analysis, leading most recently to studies of hominin and wild primate teeth in which the structural and chemical records of birth, nursing, stress, and exposure to toxins can be linked directly to the timing and magnitude of seasonal cycles on a weekly scale.

Tracing Human and Animal Movements Using Laser-Ablation Strontium Isotope Analyses

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Strontium isotope ratios ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) are a useful tracer in archaeological research to assess the geographic origin and movement of humans, animals, and materials across geologically different areas. Laser-ablation mass spectrometry allows for the rapid and minimally destructive analysis of a large range of different sample materials, including bioapatites such as teeth and bones. However, finding suitable standard materials, quantifying diagenetic overprint, and correcting for analytical interferences remains challenging. Here we report on our ongoing method development for strontium isotope analysis via laser-ablation for archaeological applications. We tested geochemical markers to detect diagenetic alterations using comparative analyses of modern and archaeological samples. Furthermore, we investigated analytical interferences that can arise from polyatomic compounds ($^{40}\text{Ca}^{31}\text{P}^{16}\text{O}$ and/or $^{40}\text{Ar}^{31}\text{P}^{16}\text{O}$) during the laser-ablation analyses of teeth and bones. We performed validation studies using solution analyses and samples of known origin to quantify and correct for this interference for a suite of bioapatite materials. Building on these results we developed an analytical protocol to overcome these constraints, providing accurate reconstructions of origin and movement for prehistoric humans and animals.

Building Strontium Isoscapes for Archaeological Provenance Studies

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Strontium isotope ratios ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) are used as a geochemical tracer to identify the geographic origin of materials, such as human and animal remains, in archaeology, ecology, and forensic sciences. The underlying principle is that strontium isotope ratios will vary among different geographic regions depending on the age and geochemical composition of the underlying geology. However, the strontium isotope pool for a specific region is often influenced by the type and duration of bedrock weathering and atmospheric deposition, such as precipitation and dust. Consequently, before this tool can be applied for a scientific study detailed baseline maps of the spatial variability of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ values for the region in question are needed.

Over the last ~10 years the coverage of highly detailed strontium isotope maps and predictive models has increased rapidly and several databases (IsoArch, IRHUM, WaterIsotopes) are now available to facilitate collaboration among different scientific disciplines and research groups. Here I report on the history and current trajectory of strontium isoscape mapping worldwide, with a focus on the contributions made by Rainer Grün to build, share, and utilize these maps and predictive models for archaeological research.

Towards a Pretreatment for Radiocarbon Dating Tooth Enamel

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Radiocarbon dating bone that is more than a few thousand years old in tropical and arid regions is hampered by the rapid degradation of the protein normally targeted for dating. Sometimes, a few bones with a little protein can be found after screening large numbers of bones. However, we often find that no collagen remains. This can result in low quality chronologies where the only samples available for radiocarbon dating are poorly associated with the event of interest, such as charcoal from burial contexts. Tooth enamel may provide an alternative skeletal material to radiocarbon date. Unfortunately, relatively little work has examined how enamel, or how carbonate contaminants can be removed. Dates are rarely accurate: typically at least 5-10% of the carbon in enamel is a contaminant after routine pretreatment. This causes a sample of >50 ka to appear 20 ka. This presentation will explore new methods to clean tooth enamel based on a more thorough understanding of enamel diagenesis. It will show that ages on tooth enamel can be drastically improved, but that accurate dates are not yet obtained. Typically the equivalent of around 1% of the carbon in enamel is modern in age after the most successful pretreatment attempted. By comparison to the radiocarbon data, it will also demonstrate that stable carbon isotopes are also affected by contamination, often by around 2‰.

Dating, Isotope Analysis and Elemental Mapping of Archaeologically-Relevant Carbonates by LA-ICP-MS: Introduction to the RIF Lab at the University Of Queensland

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Following the recent installation of new strategic facilities jointly funded by the University of Queensland and Griffith University, we have developed new laser ablation (LA)-ICPMS capabilities for *in situ* U-Th and U-Pb dating, Sr isotope analysis and elemental mapping of carbonate minerals (often pure calcites) for archaeological, palaeoenvironmental and conventional earth science applications. The instrument routinely achieves high sensitivity with low backgrounds, enabling carbonates and fossil teeth <0.5Ma to be dated by the LA-MC-ICPMS U-Th method, and carbonates >0.5 Ma to be dated by the LA-MC-ICPMS or LA-Q-ICPMS U-Pb method, both with very high throughput. Compared with the labour-intensive isotope dilution dating methods involving total sample digestion and chemical separation, this ultra-fast approach does not require extensive separation or any chemical processing, and is therefore almost non-destructive. Preliminary results from case studies involving both U-Th and U-Pb dating will be reported. Apart from the new dating capabilities, we have also developed the analytical protocols for *in situ* LA-MC-ICPMS Sr isotope analysis of fossil teeth, clam shells and other high-Sr carbonates, as well as *in situ* LA-Q-ICPMS mapping of various major and trace element concentrations in various archaeological materials.

Chronology Based Geomorphological Model Provides Solution for Underground Water Arsenic Pollution in Yangtze Plain

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Consumption of arsenic (As) polluted groundwater impacts more than 100 million people worldwide, particularly in Asian countries including Bangladesh, India, Vietnam and China. In the last decades as groundwater gradually becomes dominant drinking water sources due to severe pollution of surface water in southern China, the problem of high As groundwater has emerged in the Yangtze Plain, one of the most densely-populated and economically-prosperous regions in China. Previous investigations in Jiangnan Plain, which is located in middle Yangtze Basin and more than 1000 km upstream of modern coast, revealed that high As groundwater primarily occurred at a depth between ca. 15 and 35 m, and microbially mediated reductive dissolution of iron oxides was the most likely mechanism for As mobilization. Yet explicit explanations for the occurrence of groundwater As contamination remain unclear.

Based on lithological data of more than 20 drilling cores and chronological dating of six boreholes, we propose a geomorphological model of sea level change and land surface interaction for the Yangtze Plain to account for groundwater As contamination from a geological perspective. In this model, lowering of sea level during last ice age induced widespread incised valleys in Yangtze Plain, with thicknesses tapering from ca. 90 m in Deltaic Plain to ca. 40 m in Jiangnan Plain >1400 km channel distance. Rapid and large-amplitude (>120 m) of sea level rise began at the onset of last deglaciation at ca. 20-15 ka and ceased at ca. 8-7 ka, leading to fast infill of incised valleys with mildly-weathered sands. Afterwards, high sea level and moist monsoonal climate resulted in the deposition of silts and clays under an alluvial-fluvial environment, which acted as a top aquitard and helped to establish a strongly reducing condition in the underlying sands. It is the rapid aggradation of immature sediments which are conducive to complete reduction of iron oxides during the last deglaciation, corresponding to the depth between ca. 15 and 35 m in Jiangnan Plain, that leads to the As contamination in Yangtze River Plain. The model fits well the previous published As data, and provides a practical solution for the underground water As pollution in the Jiangnan Plain.